

Piotr Wojtal - Jarosław Wilczyński (Eds)

3rd Conference World of Gravettian Hunters

Kraków, Poland, 20 - 24 May 2019

Abstracts

ISEA PAS
2019

3rd Conference World of Gravettian Hunters

Kraków, Poland, 20th – 24th May 2019

Abstracts

ISEA PAS

2019

Editors
Piotr Wojtal
Jarosław Wilczyński

Technical Editor
Ewa Zychowska

Address of the Editorial Office
Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences,
Sławkowska 17, 31-016 Kraków, Poland
E-mail: office@isez.pan.krakow.pl

Copyright by Instytut Systematyki i Ewolucji Zwierząt, Polskiej Akademii Nauk,
Kraków, Poland, 2019

ISBN 978-83-61358-92-3

Printed in Poland
by
Drukarnia Kolejowa Kraków sp. z o.o.
ul. Forteczna 20A, 32-086 Węgrzce
Edition of 80 copies

Organizing Committee

Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences, POLAND

Dr. **Piotr WOJTAL**

Dr. **Jarosław WILCZYŃSKI**

Dr. **György LENGYEL**

with cooperation of Polish Academy of Art and Sciences, POLAND

Scientific Committee

Prof. **Nuno BICHO**

University of Algarve, Interdisciplinary Center for Archaeology and Evolution of Human Behavior, PORTUGAL

Prof. **Hervé BOCHERENS**

Senckenberg Center for Human Evolution and Palaeoecology (HEP), University of Tübingen, GERMANY

Dr. **Mietje GERMONPRÉ**

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, BELGIUM

Prof. **Gary HAYNES**

Anthropology Department, University of Nevada, USA

Prof. **Janusz K. KOZŁOWSKI**

Institute of Archaeology, Jagiellonian University, POLAND

Dr. **Susanne C. MÜNZEL**

Institute of Archaeological Sciences, Archaeozoology, University of Tübingen, GERMANY

Prof. **Adam NADACHOWSKI**

Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences, POLAND

Prof. **Marco PERESANI**

Department of Humanities, University of Ferrara, ITALY

Prof. **Krzysztof SOBCZYK**

Institute of Archaeology, Jagiellonian University, POLAND

Prof. **Jiří A. SVOBODA**

Institute of Archaeology at Brno, ASCR, CZECH REPUBLIC

Dr. **Sébastien VILLOTTE**

UMR5199 PACEA, Université de Bordeaux–CNRS, FRANCE

ISEA PAS

Martin NOVÁK

Institute of Archaeology of the CAS
 Čechyňská 363/19, 602 00 Brno, CZECH REPUBLIC
 e-mail: novak@arub.cz

Stéphane PÉAN

UMR 7194 Histoire naturelle de l'Homme préhistorique (HNHP)
 MNHN/CNRS/UPVD, Département Homme et Environnement, Muséum national
 d'Histoire naturelle, Alliance Sorbonne Université. Institut de Paléontologie
 Humaine
 1 rue René Panhard, 75013, Paris, FRANCE
 e-mail: stephane.pean@mnhn.fr

Marta POŁTOWICZ-BOBAK

Institute of Archaeology,
 Moniuszki 10, 35-015 Rzeszów, POLAND,
 e-mail: mpoltowicz@lithics.eu

Natasha REYNOLDS

UMR 5199 PACEA, Université de Bordeaux, Bâtiment B8
 Allée Geoffroy Saint Hilaire, CS 50023, 33615 PESSAC CEDEX, FRANCE
 email: natasha.reynolds@u-bordeaux.fr

Javier SÁNCHEZ-MARTÍNEZ

Centre d'Estudis del Patrimoni Arqueològic de la Prehistòria, Facultat de Lletres,
 Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
 08193 Bellaterra, SPAIN
 e-mail: Javier.sanchez.martinez@uab.cat

Fabio SANTANIELLO

Dipartimento di Lettere e Filosofia, Università di Trento (Trento, Italia), Istituto
 Italiano di Paleontologia Umana (Anagni, Italia)
 ITALY
 e-mail: fbasnt@gmail.com

Sandra SÁZELOVÁ

Department of Anthropology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University,
 Kotlářská 2, 611 37 Brno, CZECH REPUBLIC
 e-mail: sazelovala@sci.muni.cz

Marie SEGUEDY

Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Département Homme et Environnement,
 UMR 7194 MNHN/CNRS/UPVD "Histoire Naturelle de l'Homme Préhistorique",
 IPH, 1, rue René Panhard, 75013, Paris, FRANCE
 e-mail: marie.seguedy@gmail.com

Pavlo SHYDLOVSKYI

Department of Archaeology and Museology Taras Shevchenko National University
 of Kyiv
 Volodymyrska 60, 01033, Kyiv, UKRAINE
 e-mail: prehist@knu.ua

Programme of 3rd Conference "World of Gravettian Hunters"

TUESDAY 21.05.2019

Session 1.

Chairman: Gary Haynes

9:00	Nuno BICHO et al.	The Gravettian-Solutrean transition in Southwestern Iberia
9:30	Sébastien VILLOTTE	Biology, pathology, and behaviors during the Gravettian: From skeletal remains to paleoethnology
10:00	Javier SÁNCHEZ-MARTÍNEZ et al.	Amplifying technical diversity of Gravettian in southwestern Europe: the EUP occupations of Cova Gran de Santa Linya
10:20	Jonathan HAWS et al.	Human adaptive responses to climate and environmental change during the Gravettian of Lapa do Picareiro (Portugal)
10:40	Coffe break	

Session 2.

Chairman: Nuno Bicho

11:00	Gala GARCÍA-ARGUDO et al.	Ornamental traditions in northeast Iberia during Early Upper Palaeolithic
11:20	Dorothee DRUCKER and Carole VERCOUTÈRE	Tracking ecology and mobility of mammoth in Southwestern France during the Gravettian: the case of Grotte du Pape at Brassempouy (Landes, France)
11:40	Anais VIGNOLES et al.	Exploring potential links between technological and ecological variability during the Middle Gravettian in France (ca. 32–29 ka cal. BP)
12:00	Eliana NORWALD et al.	The Gravettian in Southern Burgundy: News results on lithic technology, subsistence, land use and dating
12:20	Laurent CRÉPIN	A new Gravettian site from southwestern France: the Fournol's rockshelter. New and original evidence of specific mortuary practices
12:40	Eliana NORWALD and Harald FLOSS	The Gravettian of the open-air site „La Sntrrire” near Macon (Sane-et-Loire, France)
12:50	Lunch	

Session 3.

Chairman: Sbastien Villotte

14:10	Fabio SANTANIELLO and Stefano GRIMALDI	The Noailles burins of the Riparo Mochi (Balzi Rossi, Italy): new insights from a techno-functional perspective
14:30	Natasha REYNOLDS	Populations in the Mid Upper Palaeolithic
14:50	Olaf JRIS et al.	A Middle to Upper Palaeolithic transitional assemblage at the Aurignacian-Gravettian transition. News from the open-air site Remagen-Schwalbenberg (Central Rhineland, Germany)
15:10	Olaf JRIS et al.	How 'Gravettian' is the Late Aurignacian? Worked Ivory Objects from the 34,000 year-old open-air site Breitenbach (Germany)
15:30	Susanne MNZEL et al.	Poster: Chane opratoire de Gravettian bone tools from the Swabian Jura and the Molly experiment
15:40	Coffe break	

Session 4.

Chairman: Marc Hndel

16:00	Paul HAESAERTS et al.	The onset of the Gravettian in Central and Eastern Europe, versus the Early Upper Palaeolithic
16:20	Petr IDA et al.	Lubn VI – new excavations on Late Gravettian site in central Bohemia
16:40	Piotr WOJTAL and Jaroslaw WILCZYŃSKI	Two models of Gravettian subsistence strategies in Central Europe
17:00	Petr IDA et al.	Poster: Epigravettian in Eastern Bohemia
17:10	Petr ECHK et al.	Poster: The Gravettian site of Svobodn Dvory (Eastern Bohemia, the Czech Republic): Story of an old site through the lenses of modern documentation
17:20	Tadeusz WIŚNIEWSKI	Poster: A new data for research on Magdalenian settlement in eastern Poland
17:30	End	

WEDNESDAY 22.05.2019

Session 5.

Chairman: Susanne Münzel

9:00	Gary HAYNES et al.	Bone and Ivory Fracture Patterns in Proboscidean Assemblages
9:20	Nina KOWALIK et al.	Following woolly mammoths – isotopic, elemental and histological record of dental enamel as an archive of mammal life history – Kraków Spadzista case study
9:40	Sandra SAZELOVA et al.	A wolf craniocerebral trauma from the Gravettian site Pavlov I, Czech Republic
10:00	Soňa BORIOVA et al.	Epigravettian site Stránská skála IV: analysis of osteological material
10:20	Hervé BOCHERENS et al.	Poster: Further isotopic insight on dietary partitioning among large canids in Předmostí: Implications for canid-human interactions
10:30	Bernadeta KUFEL-DIAKOWSKA	Poster: Functional variability of Gravettian assemblages. Usewear analysis
10:40	Coffe break	

Session 5.

Chairman: Andrew Kandel

11:10	Marc HÄNDEL et al.	First results from renewed excavations at the well-known LGM site Kammern-Grubgraben
11:30	György LENGYEL and Jarosław WILCZYŃSKI	The Gravettian-Epigravettian chronology in the Western Carpathians
11:50	Catherine BAUER et al.	Special treatment of large canids in the Upper Palaeolithic confirms a specific relationship to contemporary humans
12:10	Anna LEMANIK et al.	Poster: The impact of major warming at ~ 14.7 ka cal BP on environmental changes and the activity of Final Palaeolithic hunters at the local scale in Orawa-Nowy Targ Basin, Western Carpathians, Poland
12:20	Marie SEGUEDY et al.	Poster: Zooarchaeological study of the bone assemblage from the Gravettian site of Pilisszántó I (Hungary)
12:30	Marta POLTOWICZ-BOBAK et al.	Poster: Between San and Dniester Rivers. On the contact of the cultures of the Eastern and Western world at the beginning of the decline of the Pleistocene
12:40	Lunch	

Session 6.

Chairman: Olaf Jöris

14:10	Mircea ANGHELINU et al.	From Gravettian to Epigravettian in Eastern Carpathians: The Bistricioara-Lutărie III Settlement and its Regional Context
14:30	Loredana NIȚĂ et al.	The Shouldered Points Gravettian in Eastern Romania: Insights from the Bistricioara-Lutărie III Settlement
14:50	Elena-Cristina NIȚU et al.	New evidence of human group mobility and the origin of the early Gravettian in eastern Carpathian reflected through the recent discoveries from Poiana Cireșului (Piatra Neamt, Romania)
15:10	Pierre NOIRET et al.	New insights into Moldova's Early Gravettian: Recent results of the 2013-2016 fieldwork at Mitoc-Malu Galben, Romania
15:30	Coffe break	

Session 7.

Chairman: Adam Nadachowski

15:50	Andreas MAIER et al.	On the typological and technological integrity of allegedly mixed assemblages in NW-Ukraine at around 30,000 cal BP
16:10	Olesia KONONENKO	The Upper Palaeolithic Radomyshl' I site (Ukraine). On the question of a local variant of the Gravettian techno-complex
16:30	Larissa KULAKOVSKA	On the question of early stage of the Middle Dniester Gravettian: Mezghirtsy I site case
16:50	Vitaly USIK	The Upper Paleolithic site Korman' 9
17:10	end	

THURSDAY 23.05.2019

Session 8.

Chairman: Sergey Lev

9:00	Vadim STEPANCHUK	The Layer II/2 Early Gravettian occupation at the site of Mira in Dneper valley
9:20	Stephane PÉAN et al.	Functional features related to subsistence behaviours of Mezhyrich (Ukraine) Epigravettian settlements: multidisciplinary analyses of pit no.6 content
9:40	Laëtitia DEMAY et al.	Subsistence activities in the gravettian occupations of the Pushkari group: Pushkari 1 and Pushkari 8 (Pogon) (Ukraine)
10:00	Sergey LEV	Sites of Zaraysk microregion: spatial features and chronological aspect
10:20	Sergey LISITSYN and Maria ZHELTOVA	Polished stone implements in the Gravettian of the Kostenki-Borshchevo sites (Russia)
10:40	Coffe break	

Session 9.

Chairman: Natasha Reynolds

11:00	Konstantin GAVRILOV	The Epigravettian of Central Russian Plain: variability and origin
11:20	Daria ESKOVA	Epigravettian industries of the Russian plain: the technological shift after the Last Glacial Maximum
11:40	Sergey LESHCHINSKIY et al.	The Volchia Griva mammoth site as a unique research locus of the mammoth fauna and the Late Pleistocene environment of Eurasia
12:00	Sergey LESHCHINSKIY et al.	Geoarchaeology of the Volchia Griva mammoth site (Western Siberia)
12:20	Maria ZHELTOVA and Natalia BUROVA	The leporid "stezhki" (stepps) during Upper Palaeolithic on the Russian Plain
12:40	Lunch	

Session 10.

Chairman: György Lengyel

14:10	Firas JABBOUR et al	Analysis of the Upper Paleolithic Stone Artifacts from Aghitu-3 Cave, Armenia
14:30	Andrew KANDEL et al.	Poster: Upper Paleolithic Mammal Exploitation in the Armenian Highlands: New Data from Aghitu-3 Cave
14:40	Dorothee DRUCKER et al.	Poster: Impact of Changing Environmental Conditions on the Large Mammals of Aghitu-3 Cave in the Armenian Highlands
14:50	Małgorzata KOT et al.	Poster: Gvardjilas Klde, Georgia. Old collection and new data
15:00	Final conclusion and end of conference	

FRIDAY 24.05.2019

Field Session - Kraków Spadzista and Tyniec Abbey

Abstracts

**Functional features related to subsistence behaviours of Mezhyrich
(Ukraine) Epigravettian settlements:
multidisciplinary analyses of pit no.6 content**

Stéphane Péan¹, Pavlo Shydlovskiy², Paul Haesaerts³, Marharyta Chymyrys²,
Bohdan Mamchur⁴

¹UMR 7194 Histoire naturelle de l'Homme préhistorique (HNHP) MNHN/CNRS/UPVD, Département Homme et Environnement, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Alliance Sorbonne Université, Institut de Paléontologie Humaine, 1 rue René Panhard, 75013, Paris, FRANCE
e-mail: stephane.pean@mnhn.fr

²Department of Archaeology and Museology Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Volodymyrska 60, 01033, Kyiv, UKRAINE
e-mail: prehist@knu.ua

³Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles, 29 rue Vautier, B-1000 Bruxelles, BELGIUM
e-mail: phaesaerts@skynet.be

⁴Educational Scientific Centre 'Institute of biology and medicine', Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, 2 Academic Hlushkov avenue, 03022, Kyiv, UKRAINE
e-mail: boma.pg@gmail.com

Mezhyrich is an Epigravettian open air base camp, in Middle Dnieper basin, dated to 14.9-14.3 ka ¹⁴C BP (i.e. between 18.2 and 17.4 ka cal BP), inserted in a loessic sedimentary context. Four mammoth bone dwelling structures have been uncovered, surrounded by activity areas and pits. Microstratigraphic survey exhibited three main phases of settlements.

Pit no. 6 lies in the south activity area of the dwelling bone structure no. 2. Its content, which includes archaeological and osteological materials, was multidisciplinary studied to understand its setting up and use, in relation to the dwelling area no. 2, where it is situated, in terms of large mammal resource exploitation.

In the lithic assemblage of pit, besides the waste products, the retouched and truncated blades together with burins on truncation make up the majority, the microliths and scrapers are represented in a lesser extent. Pit no. 6 contains a set of osseous artefacts with repeated patterns of processing on selected anatomical elements such as ribs, limb long bones and tusk from mammoth and long bones from hare and fox. Results from typo-technological studies performed on lithic and osseous artefacts demonstrate technological unity with other structures of the site and functional specificities related to the butchery of game carcasses. Zooarchaeological analyses of large mammal remains, including taphonomy, provide new data about dietary and non-dietary processing evidence of mammoth, hare, red or polar fox, a large canid and wolverine.

Taking into account the micro-stratigraphical context, the origin and history of pit no. 6 setting up can be reconstructed. It is interpreted as a dug structure, filled with both stored rough products and midden made of butchery, artefact processing and hearth fuel waste. In comparing with the chronological framework of different dwelling areas, this study contributes to better understand the development processes of settlement dynamics in Mezhyrich camp site and modalities of Epigravettian subsistence behaviours in a mammoth bone dwelling settlement.